

PURSUIT: An Automatic Classification Tool for Remote Sensing Data

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Abstract— **PURSUIT (Projection Understanding and Recognition from a SUite of Intelligent Tools)** has been under development at the Naval Research Laboratory for a number of years. It is a versatile software tool designed to address the problem of automatic feature extraction and classification from remote sensing data. Although the tool can be applied to a variety of applications outside of the field of remote sensing, it is particularly useful for automated remote sensing imagery analysis. To date, the package has been applied to imagery from a variety of different sensor types including: multi-spectral, hyper-spectral, synthetic aperture radar (SAR), and multi-sensor data. Because of its modular design, PURSUIT is re-configurable and the suite of algorithms that comprise it can be flexibly combined to address new applications as they arise. As such, new algorithms can be easily added. Algorithms included in the present corpus consist of a variety of in-house algorithms, as well as standard algorithms derived from many areas of the statistical pattern recognition literature, including adaptive vector quantization, unsupervised and supervised feature extraction and classification, and neural networks. Each module contains a number of different pre-processing and post-processing options, and the input data may be spectral, spatial, or spatial-spectral. The modular design of the package allows data from multiple sources to be combined in the same overall automatic classification model.

I. OVERVIEW OF PURSUIT

We have been developing PURSUIT (Projection Understanding and Recognition from a SUite of Intelligent Tools) over a number of years as a generic tool for automatic classification and feature extraction in remote sensing applications. Although its name is derived originally from a class of algorithms, known as Projection Pursuit [10] [11] [1] [2], which is suitable for exploratory data analysis, PURSUIT is in fact a package that combines many algorithms together in a modular and re-configurable way, and it is this open architecture, more than any specific algorithm, which is its greatest strength.

To date PURSUIT has been applied to many types of remote sensing data, including hyper-spectral [7] [8] [5] [6] [4], multi-spectral [2] [1] [3], and synthetic aperture radar [9] [12]. Regardless of the specific algorithm chosen for a particular module in PURSUIT, each module in PURSUIT can be thought of abstractly as a processing framework consisting of: pre-processing, adaptive filtering, and post-processing (Figure 1). The architecture of PURSUIT is open-ended (user-defined), allowing these modules to be

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Fig. 1. Abstractly each module in PURSUIT is divided into three functional processing parts: pre-processing, adaptive filtering (one or more layers), and post-processing.

inter-connected flexibly in a variety of ways (Figure 2). As a result, sensor data from multiple sources can be combined in the same model and the inputs to a specific module in multi-module hierarchies can be derived from any processing level of any other predecessor module or set of modules in the hierarchy. Within a framework like this, one could, for example, develop automatic classification modules using spectral inputs from a hyper-spectral sensor and the texture of a spatial window from a SAR image.

PURSUIT is a niche tool in that it assumes all data image sources have been previously co-registered. Likewise, data preparation steps such as atmospheric correction are assumed to have been performed in another package. Since there are many commercially available packages that do both of the latter, we have focussed on developing a software environment that concentrates on the automatic feature extraction and classification stage of processing. PURSUIT can be easily used in conjunction with commercially available packages that perform the necessary precursor stages of processing just mentioned, and to that end we have made an effort to support at least one commercial ingest standard. Accordingly, we support data files with headers written as either ENVI Standard or ENVI Spectral Library files.

II. PURSUIT MODELARCHITECT, AUTOCLASS TOOL, AND COLOR TOOL

PURSUIT is divided into three main tools: (1) ModelArchitect for designing the modules comprising a model (i.e. defining algorithm, connectivity, optimization, and control parameters), (2) AutoClass tool (for training and testing models and model components), and (3) PURSUIT Color

Fig. 2. PURSUIT modules can be flexibly inter-connected and reconfigured, allowing multiple sensor data types, for example hyper-spectral and SAR, in the same model.

Tool (for entering user image truth information if desired). Figure 3 displays examples of the initial appearance of each tool. All options are executed from interface menus.

ModelArchitect (shown in Figure 3) is an interface that leads the end-user through a check-list of graphical forms that allows the user to define the necessary parameters of each component module in a PURSUIT classification model hierarchy. These forms are used to define the selected algorithm, the parameters needed to define its processing architecture and control for training, testing, or production modes. The forms are also used to determine the sensor data sets and ground truth to be used in training, testing, or production modes, and the location of each particular processing module in the hierarchy of modules that is the overall end-to-end classification model. Through the interface, the user determines whether each model receives input from antecedent processing modules or directly from data files or a set of data files.

Upon completing the set of forms, ModelArchitect saves a parameter file or set of files, which defines each module in the end-to-end classification module. These files are then ready for ingest by the PURSUIT main interface for training the new model, and in the future, for ingesting a trained model for testing on new data as it is acquired.

Once a user defines the algorithm architecture (i.e. the connectivity and the algorithms associated with each module) through the ModelArchitect, PURSUIT adaptively constructs an automatic classification model that will ingest remote sensing imagery and produce automatically labeled pixels or regions of interest for the user. Online analysis tools also help the user to refine models over time. Models can be reloaded for later testing when new data is available, or edited for comparison against the performance of an earlier version of the model; the system is reconfigurable, allowing an essentially open architecture for model design.

The PURSUIT AutoClass tool is designed to operate in a variety of modes, depending on particular end-user goals at any given moment. In Training Mode, PURSUIT is a means of adaptively constructing automatic classification models or performing exploratory data analysis with or without any knowledge of ground truth concerning an

Fig. 3. PURSUIT is divided into three main pieces: ModelArchitect for constructing model modules (defining architecture and control parameters), AutoClass tool, for training and testing automatic classification modules; and ColorTool for preparing and labelling data (image truth/regions of interest) for use by the PURSUIT autoclass tool during training and model validation.

image or signal. Once a model or filter or exploratory filter is constructed, the model can be preserved, and in, Testing Mode, tested on large amounts of novel data not used to construct the model. During training, PURSUIT also periodically enters testing mode to complete self-diagnostics, statistical analysis, and performance estimates on cross-validation and sequestered test data (if available). Users can manually edit filters in models through the GUI, for example, deleting elements of a filter vector, if so desired. During training, PURSUIT can be stopped and data probed manually in order to inspect the response of models, components, or filters to, for instance, particular regions of an image, an entire image, or a set of images. Displays are available to monitor these components and filters on-line as training proceeds.

III. PRODUCTS

PURSUIT produces a variety of products and statistics. In exploratory data analysis of high-dimensional data, for example hyper-spectral data, it can be used to view the impact of particular filter vectors in a model by allowing the

user to view data projections. These projections (views) can be quantified in terms of separability using online information theoretic measures [2].

Likewise, in automatic classification models, PURSUIT produces color-coded classification products that can be queried through the interface (Figure 4). Statistical summaries such as accuracy and confusion matrices are saved in the project working directory. Derivative products can also be produced through a number of menu-driven post-processing utilities (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. The Results Display contains several post-processing options, including “Extract Categories”, which allows the user to extract and display subsets of categories from the automatic classification result or from Ground Truth. (Top) The extract categories selection utility that appears when the “Extract Categories” option is selected on the Tools menu, showing a selected subset of three categories (“myrica”, “mudflat”, and “wrack”), (Bottom, left) A segment of a HyMAP scene over Smith Island, VA (channel 42 shown), (bottom, center) a Results Display showing a PURSUIT model predicting land-cover categories, (bottom, right) a Results Display showing the extracted subset categories.

IV. SUMMARY

PURSUIT can be used as either a research tool or a production tool for automatic feature extraction or classification. PURSUIT algorithms consist of both in-house and extant algorithms from the statistical pattern recognition literature, including adaptive vector quantization, unsupervised and supervised feature extraction and classification, and neural networks. Each module contains a number of different pre-processing and post-processing options, and the input data may be spectral, spatial, or spatial-spectral. The modular design of the package allows data from multiple sources to be combined in the same overall automatic classification model. Its modular and reconfigurable design means that it can be adapted to a wide variety of remote sensing applications including hyper-spectral, multi-spectral, SAR, and multi-sensor data applications. At the same time, its modular design

makes it an ideal research software environment for evaluating new algorithms as they are developed. Compatibility with at least one commercial standard (support for ENVI Standard and ENVI Spectral Library headers) in terms of ingest means that it can be used effectively to go from raw sensor data to final product, by relying on a commercial package to perform the necessary precursors such as georectification or atmospheric correction. Likewise, although PURSUIT has a number of online analysis features that render results and derivative products, compatibility with the commercial standard means that PURSUIT products can be loaded into other commercial packages for further rendering or manipulations as desired.

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